

An Explorative Review of the Socio-Cultural Life of the Sarak Community in Bindapathar Village, Jharkhand

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Abstract

In several western districts of Jharkhand, such as Dhanbad, Bokaro, Seraikela-Kharsawan, Jamtara, and Dumka, adjoining the state of West Bengal, there still exist in very small numbers members of the ancient and traditional Sarak Jain community. Scattered references to this numerically minor yet historically significant group are found only in a few rare sources. Among their present habitations, the village of Bindapathar in Jamtara district deserves particular attention.

A field survey was conducted there on 18 December 2023 under a major project funded by the Indian Council of Social Science Research (ICSSR). Based on empirical data collected during this investigation, the present paper seeks to offer a sociological description and analysis of various aspects of the local Sarak people's lives, such as the pattern and diversity of their economic arrangements, the internal and external structure of their households, social behaviour and customs, and religious practices. The study thus represents an effort to delineate, in a systematic and interpretive manner, the socio-economic and cultural portrait of this little-known community.

Keywords

Jharkhand, Jamtara, Bindapathar, Jain Community, ICSSR, Sarak, Minority, Sarak Jain

Introduction

In different regions of the Jharkhand districts of Dhanbad, Bokaro, Seraikela-Kharsawan, Jamtara, and Dumka, one still encounters settlements of people belonging to the ancient Jain community, who are primarily known as the Sarak. According to recent demographic research, this community, numerically a minority in Jharkhand, has remained largely silent and underrepresented in modern scholarship. Nevertheless, scattered references to them appear in

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some early and medieval literary works¹, in writings of several colonial officials², and in entries within various district gazetteers³.

One such village, Bindapathar, situated under the Fatehpur Block of Jamtara district, stands out as one of the principal Sarak-inhabited settlements in the region. The village presently comprises approximately fifty-two Sarak families. At the entrance to the village, however, several Scheduled Caste groups also reside. Within the Sarak locality itself, members of the Rajak and Bauri castes, classified among the Scheduled Castes, are also found living side by side.

A field survey was undertaken in this village on 18 December 2023. Through a structured questionnaire and interactive interviews, information was systematically collected regarding various aspects of the Sarak inhabitants' everyday life. The purpose of this inquiry was not merely to enumerate data but to understand, in depth, the socio-economic and cultural fabric of a small but historically significant community that continues to sustain its distinct identity within the broader mosaic of Jharkhand's social life.

Objectives of the Research

The field survey conducted in the aforementioned village was carried out under a major research project funded by the Indian Council of Social Science Research (ICSSR), New Delhi. The principal aim of this project is to present before the academic community, and thereby to the public at large, a sociological account of the diverse aspects of Sarak life in various villages of West Bengal and the adjoining state of Jharkhand, through the systematic collection and analysis of field data.

Keeping in view the broader theme and purpose of the project, the present paper sets out to achieve the following specific objectives:

To portray the economic life of the Sarak community in Bindapathar village and to undertake a comparative evaluation of their economic condition vis-à-vis the other caste groups residing in the same village.

To present a factual description of the various facets of rural life in the village, such as the structure and pattern of dwellings, sanitation, roads and local transport, electricity, drinking water and drainage facilities, shops, and other infrastructural arrangements.

To examine the aspects of public health and education, including the institutional framework and the present conditions of health and literacy among the villagers.

To explore, from a historical perspective, the social customs and practices of the Sarak community, especially those related to marriage, food habits, and the status of women within their society.

To analyse the religious practices of the Sarak Jains of Bindapathar within the broader context of Jain cultural tradition, and to determine whether elements of other religions, communities, or cultures have influenced or altered their religious and cultural expressions over time.

Methodology

The present field report has been prepared on the basis of data obtained through a structured survey questionnaire conducted among more than thirty Sarak families in Bindapathar village, supplemented by direct observation of actual living conditions.

During the fieldwork, information was collected through a series of oral interviews and interactive question-answer sessions with local residents. The survey sought to record not only major socio-economic indicators but also numerous micro-level details concerning family composition and demographic features, such as the number of members in each household, their ages, occupations, and blood groups.

Special attention was given to the physical and domestic infrastructure of the families, including the type and structure of houses, the number of rooms, nature of cooking fuel used, presence or absence of toilets, and sources of drinking water. The survey also gathered information on health issues, family planning, educational and literacy levels, and the religious and cultural observances followed within the households.

The data obtained through these inquiries, combined with direct field observations, constitute the empirical foundation of the following analytical report. The methodology thus integrates both quantitative data collection and qualitative interpretation, allowing for a comprehensive understanding of the Sarak community's lived experience in Bindapathar.

The Structure of the Rural Economy

Traditionally, agriculture has been the principal occupation of the Sarak families in Bindapathar. However, due to the infertile and drought-prone soil of Jharkhand, the irregular rainfall, and the consequent limitation of cultivating only one major crop a year, many families have gradually moved away from agriculture. Despite these environmental constraints, a number of villagers continue to cling to their ancestral profession as cultivators.

Noteworthy among the experienced and senior Sarak farmers who shared their insights during the survey are Sagar Maji, Dinesh Maji, Ujjal Maji and his son Ranjit Maji, the venerable Sadananda Maji, Alok Maji, Haradhan Maji, and Manik Maji. They spoke extensively of their experiences as hereditary farmers, the challenges of rural agrarian life, and the evolving nature of local agricultural economy⁴.

In addition to agriculture, many members of the community are now employed in private companies both within and outside the state. Among them are Shantanu Maji, Rana Maji, Dhananjay Maji, Nityananda Maji, Sandeep Maji (employed in a factory in Chennai), and Shyamrai Maji. Several villagers are also engaged in small-scale businesses, including Asit Ranjan Maji, who runs a shoe and garment shop; Makar Maji and Ajay Maji, who operate a grocery store⁵; and Manas Maji, who manages a customer service point (CSP) affiliated to the State Bank of India⁶.

A number of Sarak individuals work as priests (pujaaris) in Jain temples across India—for example, Pradip Maji and Malay Maji serve in Jain temples in Rajasthan, while Bijon Maji is the priest of the local village temple. Some members of the community are also employed in government services, such as Sanjay Maji (Chittaranjan Locomotive Works), retired teachers Nandalal Maji⁷ and Purnachandra Maji, and Mohit Maji (Indian Railways).

For those engaged in farming and other manual occupations, the average monthly income is approximately ₹7,000–₹8,000, indicating modest but steady livelihoods.

Banking and Financial Services

Bindapathar village has access to formal banking facilities within its vicinity. Alongside a branch of the Jharkhand State Government Bank, there is a Customer Service Centre of the State Bank of India, operated by a local Sarak youth, and a branch of the Bank of India. Consequently, villagers face few difficulties in availing themselves of banking services.

In addition to banks, some villagers also use the rural post office as a means of saving money. A number of families, from the affluent and middle-income groups, have subscribed to various life insurance schemes, though during interviews, many respondents gave vague or evasive answers regarding loans or insurance-related matters, suggesting a degree of reticence or lack of financial awareness in these areas.

Facets of Domestic Life:

Housing

In Bindapathar, most of the houses are either pucca (permanent) or semi-pucca (semi-permanent) structures, though mud houses (kachcha bari) are by no means absent (see Figures 1 and 2). One such example is the mud house of Rebati Maji, which remains a living instance of the village's older architectural pattern. Although many families still own ancestral mud houses, several of these are now abandoned or in a state of disuse.

There are roughly ten two-storied houses in the village, indicative of a certain degree of financial stability among some Sarak families. Joint families are also a common reason for the construction of such multi-storied dwellings. Semi-pucca houses generally have tin or tiled roofs, and most dwellings consist of two to three rooms, though in the case of joint families, the number sometimes rises to six or seven.

Figures 1 and 2: Mud house and semi-pucca house with tiled roof, Bindapathar

A few recently built single-storied pucca houses were reported to have been constructed with financial assistance from the Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana scheme. Every household in the village has access to toilet facilities (Figure 3), though in some cases, the facilities exist only nominally or remain unused. Many of these toilets were constructed under central government sanitation projects. During interviews, several respondents openly admitted that they still do not use these toilets, citing poor construction quality or a habitual preference for open defecation as reasons.

Figure 3: Modern-style pucca toilet, Sarak locality, Bindapathar.

Sources of Fuel

The Sarak families of Bindapathar primarily use coal and firewood as cooking fuel, the coal being procured at a low price from nearby coal mines in Jharkhand (Figure 4). The use of liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) is relatively limited. A few well-to-do families use LPG regularly for cooking, but for the majority, its usage is confined to making tea, boiling milk, or reheating prepared food.

Figure 4: Coal used as cooking fuel in a Sarak household, Bindapathar.

During interviews, most respondents cited the rising cost of LPG cylinders as the main reason for its limited use, even though many families had received LPG connections under the Pradhan Mantri Ujjwala Yojana. Almost every household has a designated cooking area, though the nature of this space varies: some have separate kitchens—usually kachcha or semi-pucca—while others cook in a small extension attached to the veranda. In such cases, coal or wood stoves are placed in a separate corner, whereas gas stoves are generally used on the veranda.

Electricity and Water Supply

Every Sarak household in the village is connected to the electricity grid, though frequent power cuts remain a persistent issue, not only in Bindapathar but throughout Jamtara and much of Jharkhand.

Access to drinking water was one of the main concerns voiced during the interviews. Under the Pradhan Mantri Jal Jeevan Mission's "Har Ghar Jal" scheme, most houses now have water connections. However, the flow is weak and irregular, and water is supplied only at fixed times, leaving the problem largely unresolved.

A limited number of relatively affluent or upper-middle-income households, about 10–12 in total, have installed underground tube wells (Figure 5). Several homes also retain traditional wells (Figure 6), some of which have been fitted with motorized pumps. Despite these resources, the majority of villagers still rely on a government-installed public water tap, located approximately 500–600 metres from the Sarak locality.

Additionally, a tube well has recently been installed within the Jain temple compound, located between two Sarak hamlets, and its water is used by the community for drinking purposes.

Figures 5 and 6: Underground tube well and old well in a Sarak household, Bindapathar

Animal Husbandry

Cattle are commonly found in almost every Sarak household in Bindapathar. Besides cows, some families also keep bullocks, and a few own goats (Figure 7). Only a very small number of families do not possess any livestock. Animal husbandry is also practiced among other caste groups in the village.

Cow's milk constitutes an important part of the Sarak diet. Products such as cottage cheese (chhana), curd (doi), and clarified butter (ghee) are prepared domestically and consumed regularly. Some families also sell surplus milk within the village. Additionally, cow dung cakes are commonly used as fuel for cooking.

Figure 7: Cattle and goats domesticated by villagers, Bindapathar.

Drainage

The Sarak locality in Bindapathar lacks a government-constructed drainage system, which is not unusual for a remote village in Jharkhand. Nevertheless, several families have built private open or covered drains, often connected to small soak pits or, in some cases, simply ending in unplanned earthen outlets.

Roads, Transportation, Public Health, and Education:

Roads and Transportation

Let's take a turn to the matter of local transportation. It must be said that the transport system in Bindapathar and neighbouring Sarak-inhabited villages such as Shalkunda and Karaya is, to this day, extremely rudimentary, almost medieval in nature. The nearest railway stations are Chittaranjan and Jamtara, located at distances of approximately 18 kilometres and 20 kilometres, respectively. Most households in the village own bicycles and motorbikes, and even some lower-middle-income families possess motorcycles. When asked about the reason for this relatively widespread use of motorbikes, many interviewees explained that because there is no reliable or regular public transport system in the vicinity, they are compelled by necessity to keep personal vehicles for commuting, even when it strains their financial means.

Public Health and Healthcare Infrastructure

Among the residents of Bindapathar, chronic diseases such as diabetes and hypertension are not widespread but are present in noticeable proportions. The survey also found that gastritis and acidity-related ailments are common, affecting not only older but also younger men and women. Nevertheless, many elderly Sarak individuals were found to be physically robust and active, reflecting a legacy of the community's earlier agrarian lifestyle. In earlier times, when most Saraks were engaged in hard agricultural labour under the sun and rain, they maintained strong physiques and good health. In contrast, the decline in physical activity, the growing orientation toward consumerist habits, and the increasing artificiality in diet have, in recent years, weakened both physical and mental well-being.

Bindapathar has its own Primary Health Centre (PHC), which also serves several neighbouring villages. The centre is attended by a rural medical practitioner, who treats minor health issues. However, most Sarak villagers prefer to seek medical care in Jamtara town, which, as a district headquarters, offers better government and private healthcare facilities.

Pregnant women generally travel there for childbirth. Interviews with several families revealed that childbirth is now conducted entirely through modern medical practices—the traditional midwife-assisted (daai) deliveries have not occurred in the last fifteen years or more. According to local residents, even among smaller and economically backward castes, home deliveries have nearly disappeared owing to rising medical awareness and improved access to healthcare.

Education and Contemporary Conditions

Bindapathar has within its limits a primary school, an upper primary school, and a high school, all located within one kilometre of the Sarak neighbourhood. A particularly noteworthy development is the recent establishment of a village library, which, during the field survey, was found to be absent in other Sarak-inhabited villages. Illiteracy is now virtually non-existent in the village. Most elderly individuals have received at least primary education, while the younger generation has generally completed higher secondary schooling. However, the trend of pursuing higher education among young men and women is not strong. A few young men have completed ITI or engineering courses and are now employed in other states. Notably, no woman in the village was found to have attained higher education or to be engaged in formal employment.

It is well known that most of the government policies and welfare schemes in Jharkhand, a tribal-dominated state, are designed primarily to benefit Scheduled Tribes and Scheduled Castes through various forms of reservation and social support. However, the Sarak community, being outside these official classifications, remains administratively unrecognized, they do not possess a formally determined or certified caste status under state records. Consequently, the Saraks of Bindapathar, and indeed of Jharkhand as a whole, have been deprived of nearly all governmental benefits and entitlements. This administrative neglect has generated a sense of grievance and discontent among educated Sarak youth. Yet, as of now, no concrete policy initiative or remedial measure has been undertaken to address their situation.

Social Life, Customs, and Religious Culture:

Social Life

Within the Sarak community of Bindapathar, one observes a strong sense of communal unity and mutual cooperation. Members of the community stand by one another in times of need or crisis. Marriage alliances are generally contracted within the Sarak community itself.

Frequently, matrimonial relations are established with Sarak families from neighbouring Sarak-inhabited villages of Dumka district, adjacent to Jamtara.

Instances of inter-caste marriages are exceedingly rare and, when they occur, are typically the result of romantic circumstances (basically the outcomes of love affairs) rather than social acceptance. The practice of dowry (pan prathaa), once prevalent among the Saraks, is said to have almost disappeared today. Several male and female informants confirmed during interviews that voluntary gifts or dowries are sometimes given by choice, but coercive or traditional dowry customs no longer exist. In earlier generations, child marriage was occasionally practiced, but this is now virtually absent. The wedding rituals and customs observed by the Saraks closely follow the conventional Hindu rites commonly seen among local communities; there are no distinctive or separate marriage practices. During the survey interviews, several residents, including Asit Maji, explicitly stated that Sarak marriage ceremonies adhere to traditional Sanatani (orthodox Hindu) rituals without deviation.

Religion and Culture

The Sarak inhabitants of Bindapathar identify themselves as belonging to the Adideva gotra (lineage). Oral interviews conducted across more than thirty households revealed that these families are fully aware of their religious origins and genealogical heritage. Historically, however, it appears that for a considerable period, the Saraks had drifted away from orthodox Jain practices, adopting instead many of the rituals and observances of the broader Hindu society around them. In recent years, particularly over the past five to six years, there has been a notable revival of religious consciousness within the community, marked by efforts to reconnect with their original Jain faith and identity.

A significant factor behind this revival has been the active involvement and financial support of the Jain Rajparivaar Group, under whose initiative a Jain temple was recently constructed in Bindapathar (Figure 8). The temple has already begun to play a central role in the daily religious life of the local Saraks. The sanctum (garbhagriha) houses an idol of Lord Mahavira, and ritual worship is performed twice daily. Almost all Sarak women visit the temple regularly for prayer and offerings.

Adjacent to the temple, a Dharmashala (religious community hall) has been constructed, where a Jain religious school (pathshala) operates (Figure 9). Under the guidance of Asit Maji⁸, who serves as its instructor, the pathshala conducts regular sessions of scriptural recitations, hymns, and religious discourses. Both men and women participate in these

activities, although, according to Maji, women's participation is notably higher. He expressed optimism that this gradual reorientation toward the original Jain mainstream would further strengthen the community's spiritual self-awareness.

Jharkhand, notably, is home to one of the most ancient and sacred Jain pilgrimage sites in India- Parasnath Hill (Parshvanatha Tirtha). Under the patronage of the Jain Rajparivaar group, a substantial number of Sarak residents from Bindapathar have participated in

Figure 8: Newly constructed Jain Temple, Bindapathar (right) — White marble idol of Tirthankara Parshvanath in the sanctum.

pilgrimages to Parasnath, and some have even undertaken journeys to Palitana, the revered Jain pilgrimage site in Gujarat. These journeys are seen not merely as acts of devotion but also as efforts to reconnect the local Sarak community with its ancestral religious heritage and to reinvigorate their cultural and spiritual identity.

Figure 9: Interior view of the Jain religious school (pathshala), Bindapathar.

Conclusive Remarks

Jainism and its adherent communities form one of the most distinguished strands in the diverse religious fabric of India. Today, the Jain community constitutes a religious minority, yet it

remains a vital component of the country's spiritual and cultural heritage. According to the principles of the Indian Constitution, it is the duty of a democratic state to ensure the holistic development and welfare of all minority groups, including the Jains.

However, due to the lack of adequate recognition and administrative awareness about the ancient Jain Sarak community, both at the central and state levels, the Saraks of Jharkhand continue to remain excluded from the privileges and benefits that are rightfully accorded to minorities.

The present research paper, therefore, asserts the need for comprehensive developmental initiatives for the Sarak community living in Bindapathar and other regions of Jharkhand. It is hoped that the findings and documentation presented here will serve not only as a reference for policymakers but also as a foundation for further scholarly research on this historically significant yet marginalized community. If this study, in any measure, contributes to shaping governmental understanding or acts as a catalyst for future investigations into the lives and conditions of the Saraks, the researcher will consider his efforts to have been truly meaningful and successful.

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⁴ Interviews with members of the Sarak community in Bindapathar village, conducted by Siddhartha Das, December 18, 2023.

⁵ Interview with Ajay Majhi, conducted by Siddhartha Das, December 18, 2023.

⁶ Interview with the mother of Manas Majhi, conducted by Siddhartha Das, December 18, 2023.

⁷ Interview with Nandalal Majhi, *ibid.* The conversation with Nandalal Majhi provided a consistent picture of the state of education and literacy among the Sarak community over the past several decades.

⁸ Interview with Asit Majhi, *ibid.* Asit Majhi is the teacher of the Jain religious school (pathshala) and the chief supervisor of all activities of the Jain Rajparibar Group in the village. Naturally, he offered detailed information about the earlier and current religious life of the local Jain community. Even after the field survey, he assisted the researcher in many ways through subsequent conversations through number of phone calls, for which the researcher expresses his gratitude.